

A 308

20 JAN 94

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 20 / 1 / 194 TAKE OFF 1002 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A308
LANDING 1633

PROJECT OFFICER:
AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A. KAYE
FLIGHT LEADER: M. SMITH
OBSERVER:
OTHERS: CLOUD PH: M. PICKERING
CCN: D. LAUCHLAN
FILTERS: D. PERCIVAL
VACC: C. O'DOWD

CAPTAIN: H. BURGOYNE
CO-PILOT: G. DALMEGE
NAVIGATOR: J. CANNING
ENGINEER: K. QUICK
LOADMASTER: E. HEATON.

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):
OPERATING AREA:

N W OF IRELAND

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME: 12 Z

A308 20th January, 1994

Start TIME (EM) -----	End TIME (EM) -----		HEIGHT -----	HDG ---
100155		Take off from FARNBOROUGH		
114338 (4)	-120809 (6)	Profile P1	FL200-> 50FT	270 deg
120839 (8)	-121039 (9)	K-GAMMA Run 1	100ft	260 deg
121358 (10)	-121500 (11)	K-GAMMA Run 2	100ft	070 deg
121613 (12)	-122113 (13)	Run 1.1	100ft	360 deg
122256 (14)	-122756 (15)	Run 1.2	100ft	180 deg
123004 (16)	-123505 (19)	Run 1.3	100ft	360 deg
123650 (20)	-124200 (21)	Run 1.4	100ft	180 deg
124200 (21)	-124436 (23)	Profile P2.1	100ft->1000ft	turning
124436 (23)	-124940 (24)	Run 2.1	1000ft	360 deg
125112 (25)	-125613 (26)	Run 2.2	1000ft	170 deg
125740 (27)	-130238 (28)	Run 2.3	1000ft	360 deg
130409 (29)	-130916 (31)	Run 2.4	1000ft	170 deg
130916 (31)	-131050 (32)	Profile P2.2	1000ft->1800ft	turning
131125 (33)	-131224 (34)	Run 3	1800ft	360 deg
131224 (34)	-131613 ()	Profile P2.3	1800ft->4000ft	turning
131747 (36)	-132246 (37)	Run 4.1	4000ft	170 deg
132416 (38)	-132916 (39)	Run 4.2	4000ft	360 deg
133052 (40)	-133552 (41)	Run 4.3	4000ft	170 deg
133721 (42)	-134221 (43)	Run 4.4	4000ft	360 deg
134221 (43)	-134423 (44)	Profile P2.4	4000ft->5200ft	360 deg
134636 (45)	-134739 (47)	Run 5.	5200ft	170 deg
134739 (47)	-135013 (49)	Profile P2.5	5200ft->6500ft	170 deg

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
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135013 (49)	-135511 (50)	Run 6.1	6500ft	170 deg
135644 (51)	-140144 (52)	Run 6.2	6500ft	360 deg
140337 (53)	-140838 (54)	Run 6.3	6500ft	170 deg
141014 (55)	-141517 (56)	Run 6.4	6500ft	360 deg
142115 (57)	-142615 (58)	Run 7.1	100ft	170 deg
142735 (59)	-143241 (60)	Run 7.2	100ft	360 deg
143419 (61)	-143917 (62)	Run 7.3	100ft	170 deg
144049 (63)	-144548 (64)	Run 7.4	100ft	360 deg
144740 (65)	-151108 (66)	Profile P3	50ft->FL200	130 deg
163308		Land at FARNBOROUGH		

A308
20 January 1994
Aircraft Scientists summary

Synoptic Conditions:

It was decided to fly to the West of Ireland to study the Aerosol in the high wind region behind a series of fronts which were approaching the British coast.

Flight Summary:

This flight was a successful VACC flight with no major instrument problems. The VACC laser is still causing some concern, and Colin O'Dowd will investigate it further.

A308 20-JAN-94

GPS data
08:38:48 - 16:35:15

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: VACC Date: 20/1/194

Flight No: A308 Page 1 of #6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:11:57	00	TRANS	5.0 ^{kt}	P	322	51.42	-4.62	Broken cu below Broken st cu above.	
10:16:13	01	TRANS	5.2	P	291	51.58	-2.02	6/8 sc below 1/8 sc sc above.	
10:20:46	01	TRANS	9.3	P	282	51.67	-2.50	6/8 sc below 1/8 ci above.	
10:36:48	01	TRANS	19.8	P	292	51.87	-4.30	7/8 sc below 8/8 ci above.	
10:49:36	02	TRANS	19.8	P	299	52.33	-5.60	7/8 sc below thin ci above.	
11:03:40	03	TRANS	19.8	P	297	52.79	-7.17	8/8 sc below thin ci above.	
11:17:40	03	TRANS	19.8	P	302	53.30	-8.68	6/8 sc below bund gaps broken cu below that. 8/8 ci above.	
11:31:16	03	TRANS	19.9	P	296	53.74	-10.21	Solid Haze.	
11:39:33	03	TRANS	19.8	P	309	54.02	-11.14	ci above clear to 7/8 sken below.	
11:43:38	04	P1	19.2	P	304	54.15	-11.58	4/8 ci above clear to 7/8 cu below thinning out ahead.	
11:54:24	04	P1	8.2	P	288	54.39	-12.35	2 1/8 cu below 7/8 feathery ci above.	
11:57:12	05	P1	5.5	P	286	54.44	-12.55	Change to 500'/min same as ↑ but in hazy layer.	

12.5 below

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: VAEC Date: 20/1/94
 Flight No: A308 Page 2 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:03:14	05	P1	2.5	P	269	54.54	-13.00	7/8 sc in - above hazy rough sea below.	
12:08:09	07	P1 ^{end}	50ft	R				Force 8 westerly 40 kts.	
12:08:39								Start of K8	
12:13:58	10	R2	100ft	R	62	54.50	-13.42	Start of K8 run 2. 100 2000 500 1000	
12:16:12		R1	100ft	R	349	54.58	-13.37	Solid haze above.	
12:21:08		R1.1	100ft	R	347	54.54	-13.48	Hazy CB? 1200ft.	
12:22:56		R1.2	100ft	R	167	54.80	-13.41	light Sun visible through cloud in places.	
12:27:55		R1.2	100ft	R	170	54.56	-13.24	hazy solid cloud above.	
12:30:02		R1.3	100	R	348	54.60	-13.31	hazy lots of white caps in water.	
12:35:10		R1.3	100	R	331	54.58	-13.32	-	
12:36:49		R1.4	100	R	167	54.82	-13.33	8/8 sc above thin in places.	
12:41:59		R1.4 P2	100	R	171	54.58	-13.17		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: VHEC Date: 20/11/97

Flight No: A308 Page 3 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:44:38	23	R2.1 R2.1	1000	R	347	54.62	-13.27	just below heavy sc cloud base	
12:49:40	24	R2.1	1000	R	321	54.88	-13.27	solid sc above.	
12:51:12	25	R2.2	1000	R	156	54.83	-13.27	#	
12:56:12	26	R2.2	1000	R	160	54.80	-13.02	solid sc above.	
12:57:34	27	R2.3	1000	R	348	54.62	-13.07		
13:02:38	28	R2.3	1000	R	321	54.89	-13.08	solid sc above white caps & foam streams of sea below	
13:04:05	29	R2.4	1000	R	157	54.84	-13.07		
13:09:08	30	R2.4/ R2.2	1000	R	161	54.62	-12.82		
13:27:16	39	R	4000	P	312	54.84	-12.74	8/8 sc below 6/8 st cu above.	
13:30:51	40	R4.3	4000	P	158	54.79	-12.74	8/8 sc below 6/8 st cu above.	
13:35:55	41	R4.3	4000	P	.	54.51	-12.50	.	
13:37:21	42	R4.4	4000	P	308	54.54	-12.56	8/8 sc below Blue sky above 4/8 sc.	

600
44200

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye.*

Project: *VACC*

Flight No: *A308*

Date: *20/1/94*

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13.42.17	'								
13.44.26	44	R2.4	5200	P	346	54.91	-12.57	in cloud layer	
13.46.36	45	R5	5200	P	160	54.82	-12.55	in thin Broken Sc. layer.	
13.47.39	46	R5/p2.5	5200	P	158	54.82			
13.50.12	49	p2.5/R6.1	6500	P	159	54.64	-12.39	2 contrails visible to front SB of flight dec. Solid Sc below Sunny 1/8 Ci above.	
13.55.12	50	R6.1	6500	P	159	54.39	-12.17		
13.56.44	51	R6.2	6500	P	348	54.40	-12.23	8/8 Sc below 4/8 Ci above.	
14.01.47	52	R6.2	6500	P	336	54.68	-12.25	8/8 Sc below Sunny, clear above.	
14.03.47	53	R6.3	6500	P	159	54.61	-12.25	8/8 Sc Below.	
14.08.40	54	R6.3	6500	P	#				
14.10.12	55	R6.4	6500	P	347	54.37	-12.09	8/8 Sc Below Clear above.	
14.15.18	56	R6.4	6500	P	349	54.64	-12.10	8/8 Sc Below Peak on aerosols? Nothing visible	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: VACC Date: 20/1/194

Flight No: A308 Page 5 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14.21.15	57	7.1	100	R	161	54.67	-12.02	1032mb sea state 7. 270TWS 442 KTS.	
14.26.15	58	7.1	100	R	161	54.45	-11.82	Solid sea above.	
14.27.36	59	7.2	100	R	148	54.46	-11.88		
14.32.41	60	7.2	100	R	326	54.74	-11.81	hazy solid sea above.	
14.37.18	61	7.3	100	R	163	54.69	-11.90	'	
14.39.18	62	7.3	100	R	159	54.45	-11.71	hazy solid sea above same sea state.	
14.46.59	63	7.4	100	R	349	54.48	-11.77		
14.45.48	64	7.4	100	R		54.75	-11.80	Dull hazy solid S.C. above.	
14.47.40	65	P3	50	R	169	54.69	-11.80	' "	
14.53.57	65	P3	3.8K	P	147	54.36	-11.60	8/8 sea below 6/8 twin sea above.	
14.55.34	65	P3	4.9K	P	107	54.33	-11.43	Just passing through top of the upper cloud layer some c. above.	
14.58.51	65	P3	7.0K	P	115	54.26	-11.10	Change to 1000 ft/min.	

A308

VACC

20/1/94

lot 2.

GMT	ALLEV.		Height	Dyn	STATIC							REMARKS		
	On	Off			1	2	3	4	5	6	7			
						1.75	2.5	3.5	4.75	5.0				
010624	✓		—		2208						D		Ground test	
					1175	13.36					B		with cabin	
											R		air	
					0.14	0.31					S			
											P			
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.75	5.0		D		Ground	
091500	✓			1720	702	1198	1677	2417			B	D	test with	
091630		✓		716	770	840	941	958			B	B	cabin	
				1460	2465	2434	2458	2464			R	R		
				—	0.15	0.30	0.60	0.81			B	S		
					2785	1016					P	P		
					1.75	2.5	3.0							
101714	✓		FL180	D	343	395	437							
103119		✓		B	358	352	264							
				R	2462	2446	2445							
				S	0.12	0.26	0.37							
				P	9367									
					1.75	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.25	5.0	6.0			
104310	✓	✓		D	599	1112	1404	2008	1849	2600	4092		1.15 up	
				B	510	322	363	448	363	374	406		Cabin Air	
				R	2480	2472	2470	2465	2460	2458	2456			
				S	7.02	0.25	0.36	0.50	0.75	1.02	1.53			
105121				P	9134									
					1.75	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.25	5.00	5.25		Transit	
111839	✓		FL200		2671		406	443	503	500	574			
112103				B	363	360	362	359	358	358	359			
				R	2504	2503	2507	2503	2500	2493	2492			
				S	0.11	0.23	0.33	0.46	0.62	0.95	1.05			
				P	9									
120543	✓		100'		1.75	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.25	5.00				
120952	✓			D	542	482	510	627	1150	732				
				B	350	346	360	360	370	395				
				R	1252	1253	1254	1252	1251	1254				
				S	0.11	0.23	0.32	0.43	0.65	0.92				
				P	11007.8									

1 2 3 5 7 9 1.1 ~ 1.2

GMT	ALLEV.		Height	Dyn	STATIC							REMARKS
	On	Off			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
					1.75	2.5	3.2	3.5	4.2	5.0	5.5	
121708	✓		5000'	D		444	610	496	790	767	906	
121829		✓		B	361	341	361	338	346	361	367	Run 1
				R	2515	2513	2510	2512	2508	2502	2500	
				S	0.10	0.21	0.31		0.65	0.90	1.09	
				P		253						
123007	✓		5000'	D	761	493	534	583	727	785	1103	997D
123117		✓		B	324	333	337	333	337	348	332	354 B Run 1
				R	2503	2503	2503	2504	2506	2506	2505	2505R
				S	0.1	0.22	0.32	0.43	0.65	0.9	1.08	S
				P	1013							P
124440	✓		10000'									
124709		✓		D	417	585	589	591	704	930	986	D Run 2
				B	345	327	326	327	328	350	332	B
				R	2512	2511	2510	2515	2515	2513	2512	R
				S	0.10	0.21	0.31	0.43	0.65	0.9	1.08	S
				P	981.4							P
125247	✓		10000'	D	637	416	501	517	660	857	1284	D
125509		✓		B	323	330	341	328	325	333	358	B Run 2
				R	2520	2513	2515	2515	2514	2514	2510	R
				S	0.10	0.21	0.31		0.64	0.87	1.10	S
				P	982							P
131750	✓		4000'	D	356	400	416	440	477	404	620	Run 4
131904		✓		B	330	318	324	318	327	327	340	
				R	284	2514	2516	2512	2514	2513	2513	
				S	0.10	0.21	0.31	0.42	0.65	0.90	1.07	
				P	877.8							
133106	✓		4000'	D	448	376		419		503	481	D Dyn
133227		✓		B	312	330	333	315		338	311	B
				R	2508	2509	2510	2515		2513	2507	R
				S	0.10	0.21	0.31	0.43		1	1.08	S
				P	877.8							P

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. *AB08* Date: *20/1/94*

Operator: *MF*

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SEZ.	CONC/CC	MAX SEZ.	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SEZ.	CONC/L	MAX SEZ.	
1008										RD ON
10400	500	0.5								in transit @ FL200
10500	400	0.3								
11000	3	0.5								
11000	2	0.5								
11200	30	3	0.5	35		35	600			Ice Crystals (graupel)
1123										error from FSSP 1003: FML90 ←
1125										←
11300	200	3	0.8	35		25	750			large Conglomerates
11400	40	3	0.1	35		5	800			
114340										Start P.
114433	40	0.5								FL90
114532	38	0.5								FL80
114638	35	0.5								FL70
114736	33	0.5								FL60
114835	25	0.5								FL50
114930	35	0.8								FL40
115020	25	0.8								FL30
115119	45	1								FL20
115217	50	0.5								FL10
115312	45	0.5								FL00
115407	45	1								FL90
115450	55	0.5								FL80
115545	70	0.5								FL70
115650	50	0.5								FL60
115812	17	10	0.03	5						FL50
120015	160	2	0.2	15						FL40

* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A308 Date: 20/1/94

Operator: M

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX. SIZE.	CONC/CC	MAX. SIZE.	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX. SIZE.	CONC/L	MAX. SIZE.	
120225	180	25	0.1	10						FL30
120431	190	25	0.25	10						2000'
120547	410	25	1.1	20						1000'
120810	410	25	1.1	25						end of P
120840										Start Run 1 @ 100'
120902	410	25	0.8	25						
121057										end of Run
121358										Start Run 2
121400	420	25	0.8	30						
121500										end of Run
121615										Start Run 11 @ 100'
121700	370	25	1.1	25						
121900	350	25	0.8	20						
122100	320	25	0.9	20						
122115										end of Run
122256										Start Run 12 @ 100'
122300	340	25	1.01	25						
122500	340	25	1.1	25						
122700	320	25	1.3	25						
122758										end of Run
123004										Start Run 13 @ 100'
123100	320	25	1.1	20						
123300	320	25	1.0	25						
123506										end of Run
123649										Start Run 14
123700	311	25	0.95	25						
123400	305	25	1.05	25						

* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B08 Date: 20/1/96

Operator: W

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/CL	MAX SIZE	
12400	805	25	1.1	25						
12415										end of Run & Start P21
12443										end of P
12443										Start Run 2.1 @ 1000'
12450	250	25	1.8	25						
12470	290	25	1.9	25						
12490	290	25	1.7	30						
12494										end of Run
12511										Start Run 2.2 @ 1000'
12520	280	25	1.3	30						
12540	270	25	2.0	35						
12561										end of Run
12573										Start Run 2.3 @ 1000'
12580	270	25	1.6	30						
13000	280	25	1.8	30						
13090	290	25	1.8	30						
13023										end of Run
13047										Start Run 2.4 @ 1000'
13050	280	25	1.7	25		3	150			water droplets
13070	280	25	1.7	35						
13090										end of Run
13097										Start P2
13099										end of P
13105										Start Run 3
13115										
13120	350	3	50	40	8	50	200			
13123										end of Run & Start P
13161										end of P

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. ~~1308~~ Date: 20/1/94

Operator: M

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZ.	CONC/CC	MAX SIZ.	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZ.	CONC/1.	MAX SIZ.	
131747										Start Run 4.1 @ 6000'
131800	55	2.5	0.05	6						
132000	60	2.5	0.08	10						
132200	60	2.5	0.07	10						
132247										end of Run 4.1
132416										Start Run 4.2 @ 4000'
132500	60	2.5	0.07	10						
132700	60	2.5	0.1	10						
132755	180	2.5	0.1	10						Shiges
132915										end of Run.
133052										Start Run 4.3 @ 6000'
133100	50	2.5	0.04	10						
133300	70	2.5	0.06	10						
133500	60	1.5	0.07	10						
133554										end of Run.
133719										Start Run 4.4 @ 4000'
133800	70	2.0	0.09	10						
134000	65	2.0	0.07	10						
134221										end of Run 4.4 Start of P
134425										end of P @ 5200'
134637										Start Run 5 @ 5200'
134700	50	3	15	40	10	3	50			
134746										end of Run 5 Start of P
135012										end of P @ start Run 6.1 @ 6500'
135100	35	1.0								
135300	35	1.0								
135511										end of Run

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A808 Date: 20/1/94

Operator: W

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R eff	CONC/L	MAX SIZE	CONC/L	MAX SIZE	
135613										Start Run 6.2 @ 6500'
135700	30	2								
135900	80	1.5								
140100	35	1.0								
140144										end of Run
140205										Start Run 6.3 @ 6500'
140400	30	1.0								
140600	30	1.0								
140830	880	0.5								Broad spike.
140830										end of Run
141013										Start Run 6.4 @ 6500'
141100	30	1.0								
141300	30	0.5								
141517										end of Run
142116										Start Run 7.1 @ 100'
142200	300	2.5	1.0	30						
142400	300	2.5	1.3	25						
142615										end of Run
142735										Start Run 7.2 @ 100'
142800	300	2.5	1.3	15						
143000	295	2.5	1.8	25						
143200	300	2.3	1.2	20						
143241										end of Run
143419										Start Run 7.3 @ 100'
143500	357	2.5	1.2	25						
143700	340	2.5	1.2	25						
143914										end of Run

* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. 1305 Date: 20/1/94

Operator: MP

Page 6 of 6

GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONCL	MAX SIZE	
144020										Start Rn 74 @ 100'
144100	300	2.5	1.2	30						
144300	300	2.5	1.2	20						
144500	300	2.5	1.2	25						
144516										end of Run.
144743	240	2.5	1.2	25						Start P3 from 25'
144935	220	3	60	35	6	12	125			1000'
145110	100	2.5	0.1	10						2000'
145246	70	2.5	0.1	15						3000'
145413	70	1.5	0.2	10						4000'
145556	35	0.5	0.01	5						5000'
145715	30	0.5								6000'
145858	27	0.5								7000'
145955	30	0.3								8000'
150046	45	1.5								9000'
150145	50	1.0								FL100
150237	21	0.5								FL110
150335	20	0.5								FL120
150430	19	1.0								FL130
150526	35	0.5								FL140
150620	24	0.5								FL150
150720	20	0.5								FL160
150816	30	0.5								FL170
150921	20	1.5								FL180
151005	10	0.5								FL190
151105										FL200

* DRS TIME

H 218

20 JAN 94

13:43:22

291

51.34

-4.75

FR P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
292.	468.	19.9	313.	-24.4	-30.4	335/21

GE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
298.	469.	19.8	310.	-23.0	-29.0	301/24

DEW C -28.98 POT K 310.59

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T 293.	SPR mb 469.	PHGT k ft 19.8	TAS knots 311.	TAT C -23.3	DEW C -23.3	WIND deg m/s 281/36
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IWS m s⁻¹ 35.97 IWA deg 281.48

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A308

20-JAN-94 12:15:46 012 34.70 -19.40 FR P

HDG deg T 350.	SPR mb 1019.	PHGT k ft -0.2	TAS knots 180.	TAT C 10.0	DEW C 7.5	WIND deg m/s 242 / 6
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PHGT F
K ft

-0.16

DEW
C

7.47

3.75

3.13

2.50

1.88

1.25

0.63

0.00

3.75

3.13

2.50

1.88

1.25

0.63

0.00

-40.00

-31.25

-22.50

-13.75

-5.00

3.75

12.50

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G WIDEO	H HELP
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PCASP CONC/cc

500

PCASP CONC #/cc 334
 PCASP MEAN RAD μ 0.13
 PCASP MASS $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 23.62

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
 1000

FSSP CONC #/cc 2
 FSSP MEAN RAD μ 2.857512548000000000000000.0
 FSSP LWC g/m^3 0.00024.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.5
 2D-C MAX SIZE μ 0
 2D-C LWC g/m^3 0.000e+000

94-01-20 12:54:58

PCASP CONC/cc

500

0

PCASP CONC #/cc 63
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.11
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 1.26

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.757512548000000000000000.0
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00024.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

94-01-20 13:18:38

1 0.1 10
1 0.1 10

PCASP CONC/cc

200

0

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

PCASP CONC #/cc 44
 PCASP MEAN RAD μ 0.09
 PCASP MASS $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 0.31

1000
1000

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD μ 4.45751254800000000000000000.0
 FSSP LWC gm/m^3 0.00024.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE μ 0
 2D-C LWC g/m^3 0.000e+000

94-01-20 13:32:05

A308

20-JAN-94

13:46:06

044 Ω

54.88 -12.60

AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
161.	845.	4.9	196.	0.3	0.8	265/ 9

GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A388

26 JAN 94

14:52:24

059

34.36

11.88

CR

HDC	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
348.	1019.	-0.2	181.	9.7	7.6	262/21

GE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDED	HELP

A308

20-JAN-94

15:00:03

065 Ω

54.24 -11.01

AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
116.	750.	8.1	207.	4.0	-33.5	262/13

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

VALENTIA
03953

10 -65
15 -75
20 -64
T 140 -77

100	285	21
85	305	26
80	300	25
70	305	25
60	320	31
60	335	51
50	310	41
40	320	37
30	330	46
25	330	60
20	335	72
15	340	66
10	330	33
MAX	12417	
	335	77

CAMBORNE
03808
AT 112

10 -67
15 -72
20 -65
T 169 -73

100	330	22
85	335	16
80	335	25
70	340	39
60	360	44
50	355	51
40	360	59
30	015	79
25	010	99
20	360	107
15	355	64
10	335	39
MAX	11660	
	360	108

HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 112

10 -66
15 -65
20 -66
T 178 -70

100	280	17
85	305	14
85	295	21
80	315	18
70	340	22
60	355	44
50	005	65
40	010	92
30	020	111
25	020	124
20	010	104
15	345	72
10	330	54
MAX	10520	
	015	124

UM/UNLY EGRR

12 Z

THU

20

JAN

1994

FUN

1

SMUK-IE EGRR
20 JAN 1994 AT 12Z

ELGG
06 219
08 055
04 219

SMEW EGRR
20 JAN 1994 AT 12Z

KRIJ
13 410
98 025/
08 44
15

FLHC
433
00
45

PCOO
12 376
98 022
058 3-3
11

VRBO
12 376
98 020/
078 5-5
12

USO
11 354
98 016/
08 86 3

VR19
13 331
98 003/
063 5-1
14

11 1 289
70 005/
-05

53.9N08.7E	55.0N02.1E
DBB1 04 220 087	GWKE 06 238 98 008/ 05 06
54.7N10.0E	54.5N11.4E
DBBC 04 215 01	Y3CH 03 218 01
03 04	02 04

20 JAN 1994 AT 12Z

